

CHARACTER STATES MATRIX

	0	0	1	1	2	2	3	3																													
	1	5	0	5	0	5	0	5																													
<i>Acanthocnemus</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	?	?							
<i>Tenebroides</i>	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0						
<i>Tilloidea</i>	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1				
<i>Clerus</i>	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1		
<i>Zenodosus</i>	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	2	
<i>Archaeozenodosus</i>	1	?	?	1	2	0	0	?	?	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	?	0	0	0	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	
<i>Cretozenodosus</i>	?	?	0	1	2	0	?	?	?	?	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	?	0	0	0	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	
<i>Mesozenodosus</i>	1	?	?	1	2	0	0	?	?	?	0	0	0	0	?	1	0	0	0	0	?	0	0	0	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	
<i>Thanerosus</i>	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	1	?	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	
<i>Thaneroclerus</i>	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	2		
<i>Cyrtinoclerus</i>	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	1	?	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	?	?		
<i>Meprinogenus</i>	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	1	?	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	?	?	
<i>Neoclerus</i>	1	1	0	1	2	1	0	1	?	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	?	?	
<i>Viticerus</i>	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	?	?	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	?	?		
<i>Onerunka</i>	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	1	?	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	?	?	1	1	0	1	?	?	
<i>Compactoclerus</i>	1	1	0	0	2	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	?	?
<i>Isoclerus</i>	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	2	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	?
<i>Ababa</i>	1	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	?	0	0	0	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	?
<i>Parathaneroclerus</i>	1	1	0	0	2	0	0	2	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	?

CHARACTER LIST

1. Anterior edge of head: straight, without 'horns' at sides = 0; medially emarginate, with frons with 'horns' at sides = 1.
2. Gular sutures: narrowly separated at base, subparallel = 0; widely separated at base, convergent = 1.
3. Eye: not emarginate = 0; deeply emarginate anteriorly = 1.
4. Eye: not exceeding contour of head (flat) = 0; exceeding contour of head (elevate) = 1.
5. Antenna: non-clubbed = 0; serrate = 1; clubbed = 2. [nonadditive].
6. Antenna: 11-segmented = 0; 10-segmented = 1.
7. Mandible: unidentate = 0; bidentate = 1.

8. Terminal palpomere of labial palps: coniform = 0; securiform = 1; truncate = 2. [nonadditive].
9. Maxilla: lacinia simple = 0; lacinia divided ('lamina present') = 1.
10. Prothorax, lateral carina: present = 0; absent = 1.
11. Pronotum (concavities or depressions): absent = 0; present = 1.
12. Depressions along notosternal suture: absent = 0; present = 1; present, with infrared receptor organ = 2. [nonadditive].
13. Procoxal cavities externally: open = 0; closed = 1; imperfectly closed = 2. [nonadditive].
14. Procoxa: transverse = 0; subspherical = 1.
15. Mesocoxal cavities: open = 0; closed = 1.
16. Protarsus: tarsomeres 1-4 moderate sized = 0; tarsomeres 1-4 shortened and widened, tarsus compact = 1.
17. Protarsomere 4: as long as 3 = 0; shorter than 3 = 1.
18. Middle leg; lobes in tarsomeres 1-4: absent = 0; present = 1.
19. Tarsal claw: simple = 0; dentate = 1.
20. Tarsal pattern, male: 5-5-5 = 0; 5-4-4 = 1; 4-5-5 = 2. [nonadditive].
21. Ultimate tarsomere as long as or longer than previous joints together: present = 0; absent = 1.
22. Base of femur prolonged to base of trochanter: absent = 0; present = 1.
23. Elytra, basal third: without depressions = 0; with depressions = 1.
24. Elytral gibbae: absent = 0; present = 1.
25. Elytral sculpture: regular = 0; irregular = 1.
26. Elytra (colour): unicolorous = 0; with colour pattern = 1.
27. Wing, 'wedge' cell: present = 0; absent = 1.
28. Radial cell: present = 0; absent = 1.
29. Aedeagus: inverted (ventrally open) = 0; uninverted (dorsally open) = 1.
30. Tegmen: in single part = 0; in three parts = 1.
31. Tegment, median strut: present = 0; absent = 1.
32. Tegment, lateral struts: present = 0; absent = 1.
33. Abdomen: Five ventrites = 0; Six ventrites = 1.
34. Abdominal segment IX: fully developed = 0; reduced to 'spicular fork' = 1.
35. Larval urogomphi: hooked, present = 0; absent or strongly reduced in size = 1.
36. Larval mandible: prosthema multispinose = 0; bispinose = 1; prosthema absent or minute with single spine = 2.